

Traceability and Quality Monitoring throughout the Fish Value Chain

D5.2 TraceMyFish Data Platform v1.0

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ACRONYMS LIST

API	Application Programming Interface
AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
IoT	Internet-of-Things
CSV	Comma-separated Values (document)
REST	Representational State Transfer

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present report provides an overview of the TraceMyFish Data Platform and the respective architectural and technical choices for implementing it. The drivers for defining the platform were the general requirements for the envisioned iFMS, the sensing solutions defined in the context of WP3, and the data specifications as elicited from the relevant work on WP2 of the project, *Tracking hazards & potential measures*.

Within the report, the architecture for the TraceMyFish data platform and its main components is presented and described, while the technologies and frameworks comprising the TraceMyFish software stack are specified. As the experimental testing and piloting over the platform and the data it generates evolves, more specific methodological solutions will emerge and will be incorporated in the platform. Accordingly, iterative updates on the documentation accompanying the platform's software will be applied and made available via the repositories hosting the platform's codebase.

1 INTRODUCTION

TraceMyFish aims to advance supply system in three geographically distributed blue bioeconomy value chains, by designing and implementing an iFish Management System (iFMS) that will allow the tracking and tracing of safety and quality-critical information across the links of the targeted value chains. Moreover, the TraceMyFish iFMS will establish a secure, trust-enabled data infrastructure, which will collect, pre-process and analyse data coming from innovative, portable sensing devices of different nature and modality (spectral imaging, variegating IoT sensors) and informing specialized AI models and architecture that will enable timely risk prediction to different value chain actors. The examined fish products will carry smart barcodes that, in communication with the iFMS, will carry safety information related to each product and will allow stakeholders and consumers to easily and reliably access this information at any time.

Towards this objective, data management and analysis are crucial for the accurate, timely and secure production and presentation of insights to the users at different stages of the value chain, via easy-to-use interfaces. In this context, WP5 aims to put in place the infrastructure that will realise the data storage and analytics functions required by the platform, develop, train and deploy the AI components that will power the recommendation and decision support features, and build the user-facing applications that will provide access to the data collected throughout the targeted value chains along with the recommendations to the human monitoring a given value chain link.

Building on the architectural specification reported in the relevant D5.1 deliverable, D5.2 accompanies the first deployment of the TraceMyFish Data Platform components. It reports on the technologies used and their organisation and communication mechanisms and specifies next steps for the evolution of the platform as it is operationalised in the context of the TraceMyFish pilots. In more detail, Section 2 showcases the alignment of the deployed components with the architectural specification. Section 3 presents technical details on the implementation of each component and the way its functionality is exposed/connected within the overall platform. Finally, Section 4 summarises and presents the main strands of activity towards the second and final version of the Data Platform.

2 UPDATED ARCHITECTURAL SPECIFICATION

As the main technical constituents and the testing scenarios solidified in the course of the project thus far, the architectural design of the overall platform evolved to adapt to the more concrete needs of the TMF use cases and pilots, building on the initial conceptual design.

The updated architecture is depicted in the following figure.

Figure 1: TraceMyFish high-level architecture

The main steps in the operational workflow of the platform are summarized in Figure 2 and described below.

Figure 2: TraceMyFish operational workflow

In short, the data collection process is initialized by the association of a *product unit* (e.g., a parcel or batch) with a unique URL-encoded barcode. The barcode accompanies the unit and links to the collected and inferred information for the unit as measurements are collected in the designated points across the value chain. At that point, measurements are initially transferred at the Videometer Cloud. From there, they are transferred as-is to the TraceMyFish cloud storage. They are validated and pre-processed before being added to the data series used as input to the TraceMyFish models, which assess the status of the product based on the data points thus far. Finally, data aggregates and predictive results are exposed to the user-facing applications through the TraceMyFish API. Each measurement is associated with the parcel, the timepoint of the measurement and the actor active in the specific step of the Value Chain.

The TraceMyFish platform is able to ingest data from different streams, including directly communicating sensors, mobile applications, web applications and cloud-based systems. Data Ingestion is carried out by the respective calls to the TraceMyFish API, accessed via the AAI mechanisms of the iFMS, integrated with the respective AAI mechanisms of the client application (e.g., the VideoMeter Lab software). The data are sent in a tabular object format (CSV) to the Quantum platform to undergo further analysis by the Quantum Pipelines for Pre-processing and Analysis. Analytical results and responses to custom user queries are again carried out via calls to the TraceMyFish API, this time for data consumption but always under the AAI infrastructure of the platform. Data and Analysis Results are exposed via an Authorization-enabled REST API, in order to ensure controlled access to the data by the iFMS user-facing applications and third-party tools in the future. The API will be implemented in PHP, using the Laravel framework¹.

¹ <https://laravel.com>

3 TECHNOLOGIES

3.1 DATA REPRESENTATION

The data exchange format used throughout the TraceMyFish Data Platform is the widely used JSON specification, as it is particularly suited for web applications and facilitates further extensions and connections with third-party and future applications.

3.2 COMMUNICATION APIS

The APIs providing controlled access to the data platform are implemented in PHP using the Laravel framework². The API entails calls for the following operations:

1. Register a device
2. Register a parcel and generate a URL-encoded barcode for it
3. Submit data measurements for the parcel
4. Retrieve timeseries data for a parcel
5. Retrieve predictive results for a parcel at a timepoint
6. Retrieve accumulative results for an actor (all parcels associated with the specific actor)

3.3 PROCESSING AND ANALYTICS PIPELINE

The pre-processing components of the TraceMyFish iFMS are incorporated into an instantiation of the Quantum data platform. They are responsible for the preparation of the incoming data streams before further analysis is possible. On the one hand, the components deal with the identification and annotation/elimination of outlier measurements and identification of gaps in measurement timeseries. On the other hand, harmonization components are responsible for transforming the input data in the representation that will be used for ingesting them in the appropriate persistent storage mechanisms as described below. Communication between the pipeline components is implemented through the use of an Apache Kafka³ infrastructure for message passing via a message bus monitored by all components.

The AI Pipeline encapsulates all modules responsible for the analysis of the incoming data towards producing predictions and recommendations for assessing food condition and applying mitigative actions in case a hazard is identified. The modules are organised under a workflow that facilitates their re-training in timely intervals as more data and analyses become available, minimising the effort for training, validating and re-deploying the trained models. They are implemented as Python and R scripts and deployed as Docker containers integrated into the overall Quantum pipeline and its message bus.

3.4 PERSISTENT STORAGE

At the present stage, the data platform incorporates two persistent storage mechanisms, one for storing raw data as delivered by the TMF API and one for storing processed data and analytical results.

The first data store is a MongoDB⁴ deployment, to which the incoming data are deposited via the downstream API. A NoSQL Database (is used for storing the raw measurement timeseries as delivered by the sensing devices and the applications feeding data in the platform and exported by the pre-processing pipeline.

A ledger infrastructure based on the Hyperledger Fabric platform⁵ is used for installation-bound analytics and processed data, to ensure security and history immutability and preservation. For the purposes of the pilots, the ledger does not enforce a strict contract. This will be determined after the first round of pilots that will present more clearly the needs and verification requirements of each actor in the handled chains.

² <https://laravel.com/>

³ <https://kafka.apache.org>

⁴ <https://www.mongodb.com>

⁵ <https://www.hyperledger.org/use/fabric>

3.5 FRONTEND TECHNOLOGIES

The first version of the iFMS user interface is implemented as an RShiny⁶ application, in order to facilitate the integration with the outputs of the predictive components. The application uses the calls defined in the TraceMyFish API to consume directly or combine data towards producing the relevant visualizations and information to each end user type. Users at different steps of the value chain have different access rights, depending on their role in the chain. For the purpose of piloting the iFMs at its entirety, an administration account currently has access to all the collected and produced data, in order to assess the correctness and efficiency of the platform.

⁶ <https://shiny.rstudio.com>

4 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

The report serves as an informative document presenting the communication points and technologies employed in the TraceMyFish iFMS Data Platform. Consequently, it aims to provide a high-level description of the TraceMyFish technologies, with detailed documentation on the individual components to become available via online public repositories or dedicated documentation websites (especially in the case of the TraceMyFish API). As technical provisions mature, the report will incorporate links to the online resources that will provide further specifications and usage guidelines for the platform, its public APIs and its accompanying applications. The presented version of the platform will be tested in the context of the first round of TraceMyFish pilots, with any observations and feedback, along with fixes and performance improvements, to be integrated in the second version.